

THE EFFECT OF PHYSICAL EXERCISE ON STRESS RELIEF AND MENTAL HEALTH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bo'sh vaqt kontekstida stress bilan kurashishga e'tibor qaratgan holda universitet talabalarining psixologik barqarorligiga jismoniy mashqlar ta'siri to'g'risida chuqur ma'lumotni o'rganishga qaratilgan. Jismoniy mashqlar inson organizmining stressga fiziologik javobini optimallashtiradi, organizmni moslashuvchan va stressga chidamli holga keltiradi. Shu bois, sog'lom turmush tarzining ajralmas qismi sifatida muntazam jismoniy faollik stressni yengishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy mashqlar, bo'sh vaqt, ijobiy his-tuyg'ular, stressni yengish, ruhiyat.

ВЛИЯНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ НА УПРАВЛЕНИЕ СТРЕССОМ И ПСИХИКИ.

Аннотация. Целью данной статьи является предоставление подробной информации о влиянии физических упражнений на психологическое благополучие студентов университетов с акцентом на преодоление стресса в контексте досуга. Физические упражнения оптимизируют физиологическую реакцию организма человека на стресс, делая его гибким и устойчивым к стрессу. Поэтому регулярная физическая активность, как неотъемлемая часть здорового образа жизни, играет важную роль в преодолении стресса.

Ключевые слова: физические упражнения, свободное время, положительные эмоции, управление стрессом и благополучие.

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Abstract. This article aims to provide in-depth information on the effects of physical exercise on the psychological well-being of university students, focusing on coping with stress in the context of leisure time. Physical exercise optimizes the physiological response of the human body to stress, making the body flexible and resistant to stress. Therefore, regular physical activity, as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle, plays an important role in coping with stress.

Keywords: Physical exercise, leisure time, positive emotions, coping with stress and well-being.

The fast pace of modern life, pressure at work, study load and worries in personal life have a serious impact on human health. Stress is the body's response to external or internal factors, which, if it continues for a long time, can harm mental and physical health. However, one of the most effective and simple ways to overcome stress is physical exercise.

Physical exercise helps to reduce the level of stress hormones - cortisol and adrenaline - in the human body. During and after exercise, the body releases endorphins, which are called "happiness hormones". Endorphins raise mood, reduce anxiety and improve the overall psychological state.

Regular physical activity increases a person's self-confidence, improves sleep quality and strengthens thinking skills. In particular, exercises such as running, swimming, dancing and yoga relax the body, create harmony between the body and mind. All this ensures the overall well-being of a person and increases stress tolerance. Physical exercise plays an important role not only in maintaining physical health, but also in ensuring mental stability. Engaging in physical activity for at least 30 minutes every day helps reduce stress, improve mood, and improve the quality of life.

A healthy body is the basis of a healthy mind and a strong spirit! The concept of stress is a widely used term in modern psychology and physiology, which is described as the human body's adaptive response to various internal and external influences. The term stress was first introduced into scientific circulation in 1936 by the Canadian scientist Hans Selye. He called stress the body's "adaptation syndrome" (General Adaptation Syndrome — GAS) and noted that this syndrome consists of three stages: the stages of "alarm", resistance, and exhaustion.

Factors that cause stress are called "stressogens" and can be physiological, psychological, or social. For example, workload, lack of time, negative relationships, and life problems are psychological forms of stress. Physiological stress affects the body as a result of diseases, physical fatigue, nutritional imbalances, and lack of sleep.

Stress occurs through hormonal changes in the body. In particular, the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (HPA axis) is the main control center of the stress process. When this system is activated, stress hormones such as cortisol, adrenaline, and noradrenaline are released in large quantities. These hormones increase heart rate, blood pressure, muscle tension, and prepare the body for dangerous situations.

If stress is short-term, it can be a positive and adaptive response for a person. However, if the stress state lasts for a long time, various physiological disorders, weakened immune system, cardiovascular diseases, gastrointestinal problems, and even mental disorders can occur in the body. Therefore, stress prevention and mitigation of its consequences is one of the important directions of modern health care, and physical exercise is considered an effective tool in this regard.

Stress negatively affects various systems of the human body, in particular, the endocrine, nervous and cardiovascular systems, which significantly change under this pressure. However, physical exercise is recognized as an important factor in protecting the body from these negative effects and increasing its adaptability to stress.

Physical activity helps regulate the level of stress hormones - cortisol and adrenaline in the body. During exercise, the level of these hormones temporarily increases, but after the end of the workout, their amount decreases sharply and returns to normal. Such a cyclical process strengthens the body's hormonal balance and increases stress tolerance.

In addition, during physical exercise, endorphins - natural analgesic and euphoric hormones - are produced in the central nervous system. Endorphins accelerate the process of psychological recovery after stressful situations, improve a person's mood and provide mental stability.

Exercise also reduces the somatic effects of stress by strengthening the cardiovascular system. Stress causes blood pressure to rise and the heart rate to increase. Exercise strengthens the heart muscle, improves blood circulation, and helps stabilize blood pressure. Scientific studies show that physical activity stimulates the immune system, increasing the body's ability to fight infections and external negative factors. During times of stress, there is a decrease in immunity, but regular exercise can mitigate this process and strengthen the immune response.

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